

Music consumers' perspective on the fairness of music streaming services and recommender systems

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Executive summary

This paper summarises the findings from interviews with users of music streaming services, conducted as part of the Fair MusE work-package 4: "Music Consumers & Music Diversity". The research aims to understand how users perceive Music Streaming Services (hereafter "MSS") and their recommender systems. We wish to gain insight into how users perceive the notion of 'fairness' in relation to music streaming services. Do they perceive the current services as fair? Are music streaming services supposed to be fair? Is fairness important from a user perspective, and if so, what elements of fairness do they emphasise? We seek to explore these questions through 36 in-depth semi-structured interviews.

The interviews were conducted during 2024 with users from a diverse range of European countries, although the majority were from either France, Denmark or Portugal. Our findings make clear that fairness, as conceptualised by users, is a multifaceted concept. While some users emphasise equal opportunity, others see fairness more closely related to equity. All users point to the importance of fair remuneration for artists, noting that fairness entails equitable distribution of revenues among all contributors involved in music production. They stress the need for alignment between value creation, primarily by artists, and value capture by platforms, highlighting this misalignment as a source of perceived unfairness. Music streaming services are seen as having a dual role in relation to fairness. On one hand, they are seen as increasing diversity by offering a vast catalogue of music and providing smaller artists the opportunity to reach a broader audience. On the other hand, users criticise recommendation systems that disproportionately favour popular artists; this is perceived to be a result of financial and label-driven influences. Many users also express frustration with the lack of transparency in the criteria behind recommendations and urge platforms to do more to support emerging artists.

Additionally, we find that users conceptualise a good recommendation system as one that aligns with their tastes and moods, offers transparency, and allows users to influence the criteria driving recommendations. Moreover, users value a recommendation system that fosters connections with artists and other users, as well as the ability to share data across platforms. These factors underscore the potential compatibility of fairness measures, such as promoting emerging artists, with user satisfaction—provided such measures are implemented transparently and offer users more control and insight. Many interviewees understand the problem of fairness as more of a systemic one. They see the unfairness in recommendation systems as merely a symptom of wider structures of inequality. Users identify systemic issues, including profit-driven business models, the dominance

of major labels and a lack of fair taxation and investment policies as systemic causes of unfairness. Although many interviewees are uncomfortable with the perception of unfairness, they typically prioritise convenience, affordability, and access to large music catalogues over switching to platforms perceived as more equitable. Some interviewees attempt to address this discomfort by supporting artists through concert attendance or merchandise purchases, but few make fairness a decisive factor in their choice of platform. The study concludes that while MSS are recognised as contributors to diversity, they are also perceived as perpetuating unfairness through their business practices and recommendation systems. Introducing fairness measures, such as prioritising emerging artists, could enhance user satisfaction if executed transparently and with user agency in mind. However, the findings suggest that systemic changes beyond recommendation systems are necessary to create a fairer music streaming ecosystem.

List of Acronyms

MSS - Music streaming service(s)

UMAW - United Musicians and Allied Workers

ADM - Automatic Decision Making

ML - Machine Learning

Introduction

“Music is my favourite thing in the world. Period. (...) for me it's the best way that I can engage with the world, myself and have access to my own feelings and understand things a little bit better.” (RI 6)

This quote comes from one of the users that we interviewed for this study. He expresses a sentiment that was widely shared among the other interviewees. Music meant a great deal to them and held great emotional value in their everyday lives. The rise of music streaming services has fundamentally changed the music industry over the past two decades, and thus also the way that users listen to and engage with music in their everyday lives. Platforms like Spotify, Apple Music and YouTube Music have transformed music into a ubiquitous and highly personalised experience, offering users instant access to millions of tracks and revolutionising the convenience of music discovery. This shift has meant that most people have gained access to music on an unprecedented scale, with the platforms breaking down traditional barriers such as geographical limitations and high costs associated with purchasing physical or digital music. Despite these benefits, the rise of streaming platforms has also introduced significant challenges, sparking debates about fairness within the music ecosystem. Many artists have raised criticism of the platform's remuneration practices and the biases of the recommendation algorithms. The dominance of major record labels and their financial influence on these platforms has led to perceptions of the platforms being unfair, as popular artists often gain disproportionate visibility in recommendations compared to emerging talents - also known as the popularity bias. While this criticism has been resounding around the edges of the music ecosystem for almost as long as streaming services have existed, they gained new momentum during the pandemic, where artists saw themselves without many alternative sources of income:

“Spotify has long mistreated music workers, but the pandemic has put the exploitation into stark relief (...) The company has tripled in value during the pandemic, while failing to increase its payment rates to artists by even a fraction of a penny. Musicians all over the world are unemployed right now while the tech giants dominating the industry take in billions. Music work is labour, and we are asking to be paid fairly for that labour.” - UMAW organiser Mary Regalado (Ismael Ruiz, 2021).

This increased frustration among local artists is being examined in the Fair MusE research project. While the artists' perception of music streaming services and recommendation systems is well-documented (see e.g. Hesmondhalgh 2021; Ferraro et al., 2021), less focus has been placed on the experiences of regular music users (Luck, 2016) despite the significant power of the algorithms in

shaping user experiences and music discovery. This study delves into user perceptions of fairness in the context of music streaming services. Through interviews with a diverse group of European users, it examines how fairness is conceptualised by users, how MSS are perceived to influence the music ecosystem, and whether users' notions of fairness align with their preferences for recommendations. By exploring these user perspectives, the study aims to contribute to a better understanding of how users engage with recommendation systems in their everyday lives, as well as insight into how a fair music ecosystem might look like from a user perspective.

Following this introduction, the paper will commence with a literature review of some of the main discussions within the field. Afterwards, the methodological approach will be outlined, and then the analysis will follow. Lastly, the conclusion summarises findings and discusses calls for future research.

Literature review

The question of the fairness of music recommender systems can be seen as an instantiation of the question of power and thus the fairness of algorithmic decisions. In the following, we present a short introduction to selected academic literature on the fairness of algorithms before we present selected critical literature on the implications of music recommender systems. For practical reasons, we focus on the English-speaking academic literature.¹

What is a fair algorithm?

The question of fairness is a heavily debated topic across many disciplines, and different conceptualisations of fairness exist. One key aspect discussed in the academic literature is how to create fair recommender systems. Recommender systems determine to a large extent how users listen to and discover music. The recommender systems influence how artists are represented in playlists, autoplay features and in interfaces. The discussions of fair recommender systems have brought new life to the fairness discussions. As Helberger et al. (2020, p. 2) points out: *“automation and the algorithmic turn force us to revisit fairness and its meaning in the context of ADM [automatic-decision making]”*. Within the field of fair machine learning, the interest in evaluating ‘algorithmic fairness’ has increased over the past years, and our research can be seen as a part of that endeavour; trying to explore how to evaluate the fairness of recommender systems within the music streaming industry. Lundgard (2020) points out that most scholars within this field tend to draw on Rawls (1971) theory of distributive justice. This theoretical approach constructs ‘fairness’ or ‘justice’ as a matter of resource allocation, thus making the right solution about finding a way to reallocate resources more equally among a group.

Scholars favouring the capabilities approach to ‘justice’ or ‘fairness’ emphasise that fairness is more than just reallocating resources. Capability theorists highlight that justice is about more than just ‘allocating resources’ but about people’s *“real opportunities to achieve valuable states of ‘being and doing”* through set resources (Lundgard 2020, p. 19). Thus, from a capability perspective, one would emphasise that a fair music ecosystem is not merely created through ensuring an equal opportunity of e.g. artists being recommended to users. While this would be considered a part of it, one would

¹ We focused mainly on English-speaking literature which means that relevant literature might have been omitted. This limitation holds an interesting discussion of fairness within the academic field that in many ways relates to the discussion of fairness within the music system (see e.g. Di Bitetti and Ferreras (2016); Lui and Buckingham (2022))

also need to explore whether this reallocation turns into real opportunities for artists to actually make use of this opportunity in relation to their heterogeneous placements within social, economic and political contexts. Lundgard (2020) proposes the capability approach as a way to overcome some of the problems and highlight how this means that one needs to include the affected stakeholders more directly. Katell et al. (2020, p. 45) point out that *“many meaningful interventions toward equitable algorithmic systems are non-technical”* and that local communities might derive more value from localised and context-sensitive solutions rather than ‘scalable’ and ‘generalisation’ solutions. Selbst et al. (2019, p. 60-63) present a list of five ‘abstraction traps’ that fair machine learning researchers should avoid. Hanna et al. (2020, p. 52) make a similar point by saying that *“we must take care not to present algorithmic equity as a problem that can be solved with more accurate surveillance systems”*. Hanna et al. further highlight the limitations of current methodologies, which rely on the formal encoding of different protected groups, e.g. racial groups, which overlook the social, historical and politically constructed nature of the category by rendering it merely as a fixed attribute.

Thus, forgetting that what it means to be *racialised*, as a social process, might differ widely depending on context. Hanna et al. (2020, p. 501) add that the focus on fairness as an abstract and technical fix might also indirectly serve to minimise focus on *“the structural conditions that underpin the problems of algorithmic unfairness”*. Many scholars (e.g. Dolsman and Lin, 2017; Colangelo, 2023) have called out the tendency of ‘fairness’ being used by policymakers in very vague ways without providing any concrete definition of what ‘fairness’ means. They also point to the fact that many conceptualisations of ‘fairness’ are contradictory to some of the basic tenets of competition law. Thus, attempts to create fair algorithms should require being explicit about what ‘fairness’ means and about the potential conflicts of interest with other (maybe opposing) interests at stake (see also Friedler et al., 2016).

Users and MSS recommendation systems

A range of studies have already explored how users navigate MMS’ platforms recommendation systems. Pink and Mackley (2013) highlight how today most households’ everyday lives can be understood as completely ‘media-saturated’. Thus, media - and in many cases, their recommendation systems - should be understood as deeply embedded into our everyday lives. Drott (2018, p. 1) describes recommendation systems and curation systems as having the following role in everyday life: *“as means of producing and reproducing consumer desire”*. On the other hand, Luck (2016) highlights how music recommendation systems can be understood not just as meant to ‘reproduce desire’ but also as a way to ‘safeguard’ the user, not to be overwhelmed by the unlimited choice of music or other media. Luck (2016) argues that music recommender systems can be seen

as a solution to what Schwartz (2004) calls the 'paradox of choice', by once again 'limiting' the choices the user has to make. Luck (2016) also highlights how people, when presented with unlimited possibilities, end up turning back to the same songs. Ward et al. (2014) also find a similar tendency among users; while many users say they want new and novel music, in fact, they prefer what is familiar.

While some scholars conceptualise algorithms as 'traps' that serve to 'hook' users' attention on the given platforms for as long as possible (Seaver, 2019), other scholars have nuanced these claims by emphasising a more dynamic relationship between users and algorithms. Siles (2023) explores how users in Costa Rica navigate 'living with algorithms' and highlights how we need to move beyond a simplified notion of algorithms of *doing something to us* to a more nuanced understanding of a dual-relationship, where users also affect the algorithms. Porcaro et al. (2024) also provides an interesting focus on the *impact* of recommender systems in shaping our tastes, our openness to new music and our 'literacy' of different genres, thus emphasising the educational/developmental role that recommender systems can also be seen to play in everyday lives.

While these algorithms are celebrated for their ability to curate playlists and recommend songs tailored to individual tastes, they are also criticised for reinforcing popularity biases and perpetuating systemic inequalities. As these platforms continue to grow and evolve, the question of how to balance user satisfaction with fairness to artists and other stakeholders remains a pressing concern. Ren et al. (2019) tries to develop an innovative two-sided value methodology for recommendation systems to ensure that both users and artists gain value from the recommendations. The goal of the platforms and the algorithms seems no longer just to optimise user utility, but also to optimise artists' utility of the platforms - and in that sense, the fairness for both "users".

Mehrotra et al. (2018) present Spotify and other MSS services as intermediaries that connect user and supplier, and the recommendation systems as their main 'value-addition' by how they 'match' user and 'buyer'. In their study, they seek to evaluate the trade-off between interests: Consumer relevance, supplier fairness and its impact on consumer satisfaction. Thus, the question of fairness is mostly presented as an interest originating from the supplier, in this case, the musicians and artists. They argue that "*exposing all suppliers equally might severely impact consumer satisfaction*" (Mehrotra et al. 2018, p. 2244). In their study, they operationalise *relevance* and *satisfaction* as limited to exploring actual user behaviour on the platform, e.g. user interaction with tracks within a recommendation set. While this says a lot about the immediate relevance of recommendations, it does not give as much information about the more in-depth desires that users have for recommendation services and what drives these interactions. Our research seeks to examine these

assumptions: Is fairness only a concern for the musicians and artists? Would equal exposure be contradictory to consumer needs?

Drott (2018) points out how streaming platforms, through marketing, seek to create desire for their curation services by emphasising that *the next song matters*. While it's important to the streaming platforms, he writes, it is still unclear if it actually matters to the users. To what extent does the desire for curation exist among users? What is a good recommendation for them, and is there really a trade-off between user satisfaction and fairness? This topic thus requires further research, and the following paper can be seen as a first step.

Methodology

In this section we present the methodological approach of this study. Thus, we cover the method of data collected, the analytical strategy, as well as reflect on the limitations of the chosen method.

Doing qualitative interviews

This study is based on 36 semi-structured interviews with users from a range of European countries. This method of data collection was chosen because the qualitative data gives us the ability to gain an in-depth understanding of how users perceive music streaming services and of their everyday experiences with the services' recommender systems. Before the first test interviews, a preliminary interview guide was created. After the completion of test interviews, the interview guide was progressively updated as new but relevant perspectives emerged from the held interviews. The dynamic semi-structured format enabled a more open conversation between us and the interviewees, where we could follow emerging themes that arose during the interviews. This implies that not all interviewees responded to the same list of questions, but it means that the conversation with interviewees became rich and nuanced as we allowed for many different perspectives to emerge.

After briefing interviewees and obtaining consent, we ask general questions about the interviewees' listening habits in their everyday life routine before asking more specific questions about which streaming service they use. Then we enquired about their experiences with the platform(s) in question, and specifically the recommendation system. Here we also explored their music preferences, habits and ways of discovering music. From here, we moved on to the question of fairness. First, we explored fairness in general and then moved on to inquire about their perception of music streaming platforms and recommendation systems in relation to fairness. In the final part of the interview, we asked most interviewees what they would change/keep if they were the boss of their streaming platform to explore what they believed were the steps needed to be taken towards a fairer music ecosystem.

We mainly conducted interviews via video call service (Teams and Google Meet). Three interviews were conducted in person. In total, almost 17 hours of interview data were collected, with the average interview taking around 28 min. The shortest interview time was 13 minutes and the longest lasted 51 minutes. The interviews were conducted in the language that best suited the participant: English, French, Danish or Portuguese. The interviews were mainly conducted by two research assistants, one located in France and one located in Denmark, during 2024. A few interviews were also

conducted by two research interns connected to the consortium in Denmark and Portugal respectively. All interviews have been anonymised to protect interviewees' privacy and have been numbered. Thus, in the text, the interviews will be referred to as Research Interview (RI) and their number, e.g. (RI 1).

Finding interview participants

Interview participants were recruited through several channels, and the aim was to get a broad scope of different types of music listeners. We applied several channels to get a broader selection of users. We reached out to higher education institutions, music communities, art hubs, festivals, music schools, in social media groups related to music, rehearsal spaces, as well as cafés and community houses. Some interview participants were also recruited through project partners' social networks within the different consortium countries. We used two selection criteria for inclusion and one for exclusion of interviewees: 1) the user uses one of the three music streaming platforms, either in a free or paid version: Spotify, Apple Music and/or YouTube Music, 2) the user lived in Europe at the time of the interview. We had one exclusion criterion: a user cannot participate if a professional musician.

Most of our interviewees were between 25 - 35 years old,² and from mainly three countries: Portugal (n=11), France (n=15) and Denmark (n=7).³ Even though we had excluded the possibility of professional musicians participating, many of our interviewees still held a dual-role as both a streaming user and as someone with formal relations to the music industry. Five of the interviewees were musicians on a hobby level, and a few had experience with publishing their music on Spotify. An additional 11 of the interviewees worked with music in some other function e.g. communication, research, at music venues. However, the majority (n=20) still held no formal connection to the industry. Most interviewees (n=21) could, however, be defined as music enthusiasts, meaning interviewees with an above-average interest in music and the music sector. This of course, carries certain biases, and our interviewees might likely be more concerned with the unfairness of the music ecosystem due to their familiarity with it and interest/position in it, compared to the average music consumer. However, even the interviewees who didn't have any relationship to the music industry,

² Only 5 participants were above 40 years old.

³ Additional users were recruited from Germany (n=1), Hungary (n=1), Spain (n=1). It is also important to note, that country refers to the country where the user currently resided. A few of the interviewees had recently relocated and can thus be seen as representing a perspective of several cultures/regions.

expressed that they had a sense that the platforms were not completely fair to musicians and expressed a wish to be able to access fairer platforms. We experienced that despite our few selection criteria, it was quite difficult to find interview participants, and especially interview participants with no relation to the music industry. We also found it difficult to attract older streaming users.

We experienced some problems in recruiting potential interviewees. Our framing of music streaming services and algorithmic recommendations as possibly unfair did not always resonate with potential interviewees' views. Unfortunately, these potential interviewees typically did not see a reason to spend time being interviewed. Our results are thus biased in the way that interviewees were already interested in discussing the topic. This whitepaper thus does not present a representative view on music streaming users' views on fairness, but a subsection consisting of some of those users who agree with the relevance of the discussion.

Analytical strategy

The recorded interviews were translated into English if not conducted in English, subsequently transcribed using automatic transcription software and human supervision. All of the interviews were read and listened to several times, and after familiarising ourselves with the material, the coding process begun. One research assistant coded the topics of interviews, following the coding practices of reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2022). As Braun et al. (2022) argue for an approach to thematic analysis that is fully embedded within the qualitative paradigm, we move our focus from treating the data as a resource to be mined by following already pre-decided steps, towards a practice where analysis is a reflective process. This process meant that we 'moved back and forth' between coding and redefining coding themes.

Analysis

Here we present and discuss the interviewees' statements. First, we explore the user perceptions of music streaming services and different ways of conceptualising fairness. Then, we move on to analyse how interviewees speak about recommendation services, preferences and habits. We explore whether or not a 'good recommendation' can be seen as compatible with the interviewees' own notions of a 'fair recommendation'. Next, we examine user perspectives of fairness as an issue that goes beyond recommendation systems. Lastly, we examine how the interviewees navigate the perceived unfairness and role(s) they wish the streaming services would take on the path towards a fair music ecosystem.

User perceptions of music streaming services and fairness

We explore different conceptualisations of fairness that can be observed in the interviews: What does fairness mean for users? Which elements and conceptualisations are emphasised? We continue by exploring how interviewees perceive the role of music streaming services in relation to fairness: Did the interviewees see the platform as an entity that promotes or hinders fairness? What are their experiences with the platforms' recommender systems?

Fairness as an ambiguous concept

During the interviews, we asked interviewees to reflect on what 'fairness' meant for them - both as a general concept and in relation to the music streaming sector. From the answers it became clear that 'fairness' is an ambiguous concept that holds many different meanings. As one of the interviewees explains:

"It [fairness] is something moral and ethical. It's both decided by people around you, the collective, and also decided by your own moral compass. So, for something to be fair it has to be both related to how you experience it but also how society perceives it as being fair (...) I also think it's difficult to have any final truth about what is fair, because it is a subjective experience that is a part of identifying what is fair. So I might think what I am doing to you is fair, but if you don't view it as fair, then it is not fair" (RI 36)

Fairness, in her opinion, is not something that can be defined or measured objectively but needs to be understood as a dynamic, relational and (shifting) ethical concept. Another interviewee expresses a similar scepticism towards uncritically throwing around the word 'fair' as he says:

“(...) there are many different opinions about what would be fair. Most people would probably like things to be fair, but it all depends on what it actually means. So, I think I would listen carefully if I hear the word being used (...) what is the background for using it? As I also did with this project” (RI 15).

While it's an ambiguous and multifaceted concept, there is still a clear tendency of what comes to the interviewees' minds when asked about fairness. The topic most interviewees mentioned was artists' remuneration. Interviewees expressed views that a majority of artists earned very little by having their music on streaming platforms. Thus, many interviewees conceptualised fairness as closely related to artists receiving fair remuneration. One interviewee points to the link between fair remuneration and recommendations: *“Fairness is about equal remuneration or recommendation... about having a level playing field” (RI 7)*. Several interviewees echo this focus and emphasise, like RI 4, that all artists should have an *“equal chance or opportunity to gain something or to receive something” (RI 4)*. While three interviewees merely emphasise equality of opportunity to be discovered on the platform (RI 5; 4; 29) and that fairness primarily means allowing everyone to have the same rights - five interviewees also conceptualise fairness as *equity* rather than equality (RI 1; 6; 9; 17; 27), e.g. as in:

“It means that the incomes generated (...) Anything that comes out of the music playing on any platform gets distributed (...) its distributed in an equity way, more than an equal way but equity way to the people who made it possible to be there” (RI 19)

Another interesting aspect that arose when discussing fairness, was that some interviewees also conceptualised fairness as a coherence between where value is created and where it is captured. One interviewee explains:

“I think if we picture this business as a cake, I think fairness would be the one who makes the cake would get the biggest part of the actual cake” (RI 8)

Another interviewee says: *“what is the main reason for the existence of Spotify? It's music. (...) I don't think it's fair the price. (...) They are abusing from the heart of others” (RI 11)*. When reflecting on the barriers for a fairer remuneration practice, one interviewee explains: *“The argument from Spotify seems to be, “You're using our platform to promote your music,” yes, but the platform wouldn't exist without musicians. It doesn't make much sense.” (RI 17)*. One interviewee also pinpoints the power balance as an issue in that the musicians have little control over how remuneration works:

“When we see the situation of artist remuneration, or that actors like Spotify have decided to demonetize the songs, to not pay the artists when they are listened to less than a thousand times per month, I think. That still raises a lot of questions to me. And I think it's not acceptable. Because, in fact, who makes the content, who produces value, are the artists. The platform is just an intermediary in relation to that. So, I think it would be normal to support, in any case, to give more chances to these artists.” (RI 2)

The interviewees experience this incoherence between value creation and value capture as unfair, and believe the artists ‘*who produce the value*’ should have more influence on remuneration. When asked how to go about bringing about fairness, one interviewee explains:

“I think the first way is the revenue, the money issues and the money distribution. I think that's probably the most important at this point (...) I also think about it in other ways, like crediting the artists and crediting the technical professionals that work on the music, I think that's one of the major flaws of the streaming services.” (RI 19)

Thus, it is also clear that fairness is not just about remuneration to the main artist, but that all the people involved in the music production get credited and paid:

“So if we're going to increase the revenues, we should know, okay, there's not only one person that's benefiting from that, but the whole team or whatever.” (RI 7)

Fairness is also conceptualised as the protection of artists' creative property:

“I think that for artists it's important that their music is well protected, that it can't be plagiarized. (...) Especially, there are many artists who have very good beats and what people do is copy their beats and make other songs. So that should be very well protected, and I think it already is.” (RI 16)

Thus, fairness from a user perspective is an ambiguous and multifaceted concept, yet it remains clear that most interviewees express that fairness entails increasing remuneration for artists, as well as extending credit and protection to artists on the platforms. Furthermore, the interviewees also emphasise that fairness means an alignment between who creates the value and who captures it. With this in mind, we will go on to explore how interviewees conceptualise music streaming services and their recommender systems. Are music streaming services seen as vehicles that enhance or hinder fairness?

MSS as simultaneously promoting and hindering diversity

“There is a much bigger diversity in what you have access to. It’s not the same way as through a record label, and that’s something I appreciate a lot. But it also has the consequence that fewer musicians can make a living off of it” (RI 15).

This quote from one of the interviewees exemplifies the general sentiment among interviewees when speaking about the music streaming sector's role in relation to fairness. Most interviewees see the music streaming services as both promoting and hindering fairness in the music sector. The interviews highlight the complexity and dual role of the platforms from a user perspective.

The increased diversity of available music and the ability for musicians and users to connect at an unprecedented scale are highlighted as one of the main ways that music streaming services contribute to fairness. One interviewee remarks: *“There are a lot of small bands on Spotify. As a user, you can even listen to bands with less than 1,000 listens.”* (RI 27). These sentiments are echoed by many interviewees by pointing to the big catalogue and the fact that anyone can now put their music on the platform, thus supposedly circumventing the gatekeeping of the record labels. Interviewees emphasise the positive power of music streaming on increasing the diversity of music accessible by pointing to the fact that even small artists have a chance of being discovered. One interviewee described how she found that the platforms and their recommendations systems allowed her a broader scope of music than offered by the traditional radio stations:

“I think it’s a nice way to be introduced to new music (...) also that it’s not just the radio hits, which feels like the alternative - where it’s the same 20 songs - so it’s nice to have more new songs that you can also discover” (RI 36)

Another interviewee explains how streaming services gave her access to a lot of music she had not been able to afford and thus added great value to her life (RI 32). This is clear from almost every single interviewee - that streaming services have offered them a way to have music at their fingertips and as a ‘companion’ through their everyday routines (RI 5; 8). While most interviewees don’t discover music mainly on streaming, some interviewees still emphasise how streaming has given them the ability to discover new music without having to pay a lot of money on concerts etc. and thus lowering the cost of discovering new music (RI 16). Some interviewees also expressed that they have discovered new music and genres through streaming and thus, came across a wider variety of music that they would otherwise maybe not have come by (RI 33; 34). A few of the interviewees also highlighted how they perceived streaming services to be less biased and political than radio stations and record labels (RI 5; 36). The comparison to torrent and piracy was also used to highlight how

music streaming platforms could be seen as a move towards a fairer music streaming industry (RI 5; 11). This opinion was not shared by all interviewees. Some raised the question of whether today's streaming services are less biased and fairer than their predecessors. One interviewee, even likens the streaming business model to the torrent model:

“Spotify's business model is just a way to capitalise on what was basically torrent's model - it's not that much different when you think about it. Like, Daniel Ek, if I remember correctly, worked on Torrent at some point. (...) The base is the same, like, have a library of music and you listen to it free. There's not a difference, the only difference is it's actively monetizing what you're doing with it. (...) I think it's a complete lunacy and almost funny how these companies were able to trick us into basically assuming that monetized piracy was a viable strategy.” (RI 14)

Another interviewee, who is also himself a musician, also expressed how he saw music streaming as having a more negative effect on the music industry:

“What I feel both as a listener and as an artist is that streaming services are actually just contributing to making the music industry more unequal - if that's even a word - I'm not sure but, you know, it just feels like things are more difficult now for an artist to break through. It's a little bit of a fallacy that because of the internet everybody can be discovered. I mean technically everybody can be discovered but for the most part artists either get mentioned on the big platforms like Pitchfork or The Needle Drop or whatever - or they come through these playlists or these ads or commercials. What streaming seems to me has done, really is they brought back Payola.” (RI 6)

The problem of music streaming services 'bringing back Payola', which is referring to the illegal practice of paying a commercial radio station to play a song without the station disclosing the payment, is also highlighted by several interviewees as a barrier to fairness:

“You pay to not get commercials, but you still get commercials through who Spotify promotes. I think this is not fair and it should be more organic, who is promoted and talked about (...) I don't think the labels should have the ability to pay for extra promotion” (RI 34).

This boosting of certain songs by the platforms is also noticed by many of the interviewees in their own listening:

“When new music is promoted, usually you hear a lot of the same artists, and it might be because - I'm not really sure how it works- but maybe they buy the ads on the platforms, or maybe they put more money into it, so they get promoted more, and the smaller artists who don't have that much amount, that much money, they won't get promoted just because they are not making the same amount of money, and I think that would be unfair. Because maybe they do have good music, but they just don't have the money to promote it like the other artists” (RI 1)

Some interviewees have experienced 'odd' recommendations where the system has kept pushing certain popular artists even when the artist falls far away from their usual music taste (RI 33; 34). One interviewee observed:

“There are some times that I think that the algorithm is trying to force me to listen to something. Like there are two cases where Spotify tried really hard for me to listen to Beyonce and to Sabrina Carpenter. (laughing). The playlist had nothing to do with that but they put their songs. (...) I felt like they are really trying to get me... forcing me to listen to this” (RI 9)

Another interviewee explains how he has recently turned off auto-play because it kept pushing the same songs repeatedly. Even though he didn't mind the songs, he felt annoyed because it felt forced that the big hits kept coming back every time he finished an album (RI 14). One interviewee has had the same experience and reflects on the label's role in 'polluting' his recommendations:

“The feeling that I get is that the labels behind these artists are paying the streaming services big time - not to mention that they also have, you know, equity stakes in these companies anyway... So, I know that they have leverage but it seems like they're pushing their artists so much that they end up falling into the laps of people who wouldn't even necessarily or at all care for these artists or for their music. “ (RI 6).

One interviewee, when asked about the fairness of the platform he is using remarks: “I have thought about how difficult it is to find new music on Spotify. It's a lot of the same songs that are configured on the playlists” (RI 34). Thus, many interviewees seem to experience that the bigger artists are pushed more, and that a lot of the same popular artists configure on the general playlists. Nonetheless, one interviewee observes that she also experiences that it seems to change depending on her search strategy:

"I think most of the time they recommend popular artists or artists that already have some guaranteed streaming - but sometimes when you listen to some really, really niche types of music they can recommend you some like independent artists - but those independent artists are relatively popular in that niche" (RI 4).

Another interviewee explains that she gets recommended a wide variety of both small and popular artists and believes that it's probably related to her taste - that because she searches for smaller artists and more eclectic genres, the platform's recommendations, for her, manage to imitate that (RI 27). Interviewee 5 observes a similar tendency:

"I noticed that if I... If I choose, like, Summer Vibes or Chilling in the Autumn, that kind of playlists, mainly the big names are there. But if I choose something more sophisticated, like Chilling and Background to Work Music and Recommendations of the Week and that kind of list, there are less known names. And I enjoy that. But I noticed that there is, like, a Hungarian trumpet player, jazz musician that I prefer, and he has just out a new album, and it has never been offered for me" (RI 5).

Thus, some interviewees experience that they can overcome the supposed 'popularity bias' by searching out different types of music. Nonetheless, several interviewees also observed that there is a barrier when it comes to recommendations across languages. Interviewee 3 pinpoints that the recommendation systems seem less trained and finetuned with music in languages other than English:

"I think it lacks some... I'm missing the word... It's not very precise when it comes to Portuguese music, for example. It gets it somewhat right, but I think the platforms tend to mix Portuguese music, Spotify especially, in like the same bag. In spite of the genre, so yeah." (RI 3).

Generally, around half of the interviewees also point out that they see a strong tendency for the platform's recommendation systems to favour English-speaking music, and that they are rarely exposed to music in other languages. This is also aligned with the fact that most of them already listen mostly to English-speaking music and thus it might be a trend reinforced by users' preferences. Whether or not users want the algorithms to push music from languages that they aren't familiar with is quite different - some emphasising that music recommendations shouldn't be limited to the same language (RI 29; 21) while others appreciate the 'barrier' because they wish to understand the lyrics (RI 1; 32). The recommendations also seem to be tied to the location, as one interviewee observes:

“They recommend, in general, I think, both here and in Honduras, I used to get a lot of recommendations from the United States, but I think that is because I listen to a lot of music from the United States, so that would make sense. And then, I get a lot of recommendations from France, and yes, it is true that I am living in France, but I do not listen to any French music, and each time, sometimes, I just randomly get a French song.” (RI 1)

Thus, while interviewees' experiences with recommendation systems are mixed, most interviewees feel it is unfair for the recommendation systems to promote certain musicians because of their labels or ability to pay. Many interviewees also express a wish for platforms to promote smaller and emerging artists more than popular artists:

“It would be nice to get recommendations of artists that would be interesting according to the music that I listen to, because it could give me the opportunity of finding say an up-and-coming artist or a rarity or somebody who's really struggling to put their music out there.” (RI 6)

When asked what he would change if he were the boss of the streaming service, interviewee number 9 suggested that he would: *“maybe give it a boost to artists that have the monthly listeners down and yeah give them more of a headlight. That could be the way I think.” (RI 9)*. Another interviewee, number 17, expressed a wish for the recommendation algorithm to act as a force for a more equitable music market, where bigger artists help smaller ones grow: *“I'd try to get people out of their bubbles, like creating an anti-algorithm or counter-algorithm where the big names help support the smaller ones.” (RI 17)*

Sub-conclusion

Our findings highlight that interviewees see the role of music streaming services in creating a fairer music ecosystem as complex and multifaceted. While many interviewees emphasise how streaming services have promoted more fairness and diversity in the music industry, the same interviewees also pinpoint several barriers to fairness, such as artists' remuneration, biased recommendation systems and the influence of labels and financing on who gets promoted. Interviewees also express that while the recommendation systems allow them to discover new things, it still tends to favour popular music, and they wish that the platforms took a bigger responsibility to support emerging artists.

A fair recommendation = a good recommendation?

As seen above, most interviewees emphasise that one of the pathways towards a fairer recommendation system should entail that smaller and new artists are given priority by recommendation systems. But how does that align with their listening habits and their conceptualisation of a 'good' recommendation? How do they use recommendations in their everyday lives, and how would giving space to a wider diversity of artists affect their satisfaction? Thus, we turn to explore how the interviewees speak about their preferences and experiences with recommendations in their everyday lives. What is a good recommendation for them - and does it align with their more abstract notion of fairness?

A good recommendation fits the mood

As part of the interview, we asked interviewees how satisfied they were with the recommendations. The responses were mixed. Around half of the interviewees interviewed were somewhat happy with the recommendations that they received, while the other half were frustrated. The interviewees who were happy with the recommendations argued that the recommendation algorithms gave them the ability to explore music similar to the type of music they already listen to (RI 21; 32; 36). As one interviewee says:

"It doesn't play the same artist again, but it continues in the same vein, and by doing that, it's often helped me discover songs I didn't know. When it's like that, I leave Spotify running and when there's a song that really moves me, that I like, I put it in my playlist." (RI 29).

It was also clear that many interviewees appreciated the algorithm playing similar music, as it allowed them to stay within the same 'mood': *"If I choose a playlist of dancing songs, I don't want to cry... out of context"* (RI 5). Another interviewee also explains how it's important for 'the next song' to fit within the flow of the other songs:

"The next song that plays should also have a similar tempo or something that goes with the previous one. It should have a similar mood, maybe instrumentation" (RI 7)

Several interviewees state that they enjoy getting recommendations for similar music, and that they don't see any need for the algorithm to try to introduce them to e.g. new genres (RI 17; 35; 7; 5; 32; 3). A few explain that even if the recommendation system tried, it probably wouldn't work as they would need to be 'mentally' open to it (RI 3; 13):

"I think I would prefer if it would give me something similar, because like I said, I have... I like to be in control. And if I'm not... If I'm in a mindset where I want to listen to something different, I will have to look for it because if it's just like... And I'm kind of... I have to admit that that's one of my flaws when listening to music, I'm usually very conservative regarding what I listen to. Like, I'm not one to just listen to something different and be like oh this is amazing. Like I have to really... And in order for me to be able to like something different, I have to be in that mindset." (RI 3).

Interviewees, though, generally seem open to discovering new artists, as long as it is within the genres and styles of music as they usually listen to. Interviewee 19 explains:

"I think it's good that Apple Music - or any streaming service - is able to give me something that relates to my personal taste, but I would like to have newer things inside my regular taste for music (...) The thing is I wouldn't want to listen to something too far away from my personal taste, but I would like to listen to new stuff - things that I haven't been exposed to - within my music taste." (RI 19).

Another interviewee, number 16, explains:

"I think it would be good if it would recommend me more niche things, for the simple reason that if you recommend something to me and I don't like it, then I tell you that I don't like it, and you don't recommend it to me anymore. But at least you have exposed me to it and now I know about that niche." (RI 16)

Thus, our findings suggest that exposing users to emerging artists within the genres that they already enjoy would not necessarily compromise user satisfaction. It might indeed also enhance the satisfaction among the users who we found to be currently dissatisfied with their recommendations. Odd recommendations that don't make sense and recommendations sometimes being 'too safe' and thus boring are typical reasons for the dissatisfaction (RI 15; 17; 14; 34). Interviewee 16 expresses: *"I'm a little bored so I would also like it to be a bit more dynamic."* (RI 16). Thus, introducing more new music from emerging artists might help them experience the recommendations system as more dynamic and rewarding.

A good recommendation is transparent

It was also clear that from a user perspective, a good recommendation was not merely conceptualised as a recommendation that 'fits the mood' of the user. Many interviewees also

highlighted that it would be nice for recommendations to become more transparent. While many interviewees appreciated the convenience of the recommendation systems, a range of interviewees also expressed discomfort with the feeling of not being in control over what they were listening to, and the lack of knowledge about why certain music was recommended to them. A few interviewees even describe having turned auto-play off in periods because they disliked not being in control of their own listening (RI 15; 33). Interviewee 3 states:

“I hate that Spotify just keeps playing music, like the suggestions, after you finish listening to something. Because I sometimes get distracted, and I realize only like two or three songs after that I'm not listening to the same thing that I was, that I chose to listen. So that kind of annoys me.” (RI 3)

Thus, this feeling of not being in control was frustrating for some interviewees. This was also clear when discussing being exposed to new emerging artists - while interviewees were positive towards this idea, at the same time they stressed that they wouldn't like the recommendations to be persistent. One interviewee explains that she would like to discover new music and be exposed to emerging artists, but that *“if I don't like it, I don't like it.”* (RI 35). Recommendation algorithms shouldn't keep recommending the same artists repeatedly, no matter if they are within the genre or they are 'odd' recommendations. This would lead to frustration and a feeling of someone besides themselves being in control of their listening (RI 9; 35). As one interviewee states: *“(...) for me, fairness is the fact that my perception of music is not biased by interests that are not my own, quite simply.”* (RI 28). Several interviewees also expressed frustration with the idea that their music taste is being affected by hidden interests (RI 4; 6; 20). Other interviewees also emphasise that they don't like the notion of their music listening being controlled by political or financial interests (RI 15; 36). While most find it unfair that outside interests affect their listening, one interviewee argues that the main issue for him is the fact that it is hidden:

“I think there is a big issue with transparency (...) About how many big media companies that have stakes in Spotify. (...) This is not the Sony Music streaming service, this is Spotify. It's kind of giving itself out to be neutral or like being a platform for everybody. But again if there are people who have like 30% stakes in the company (...) they will be biased“ (RI 20)

The interviewee goes on to highlight that he doesn't mind the platform promoting artists from certain labels but stresses that the streaming service should be transparent about what interests are driving their recommendations (RI 20). Another interviewee points out that, while frustrating, it is probably

impossible to find a recommendation algorithm that is not biased in some way. At least it should be transparent and interviewees should have more control and agency in the process (RI 15).

The need for more control and agency was raised by many interviewees. For some, the quest for transparency was less about a possibly hidden interest behind 'odd recommendations' but more a means to enhance their listening experience and ability to find new music (RI 33; 10; 15). While a few interviewees (RI 2; 9; 16; 32) experienced that they were able to 'control' or 'shape' the recommendation system a little bit, most interviewees we spoke to found it confusing and thus expressed they were unable to influence it, e.g.:

"I don't think I have enough information for me to know how to control it. I have tried but I haven't had any success. So the feeling I get is that I am doing something wrong, because it's not behaving the way I would like it to (...) I would like them to more transparent about it" (RI 19)

As interviewee 1 explains: *"I think it would be helpful if listeners knew how things work, simply because it would get us less frustrated"* (RI 1). Interviewee 16 reflects on how more transparency would also enhance his ability to find new music himself:

"I think it would be good if it was transparent. Because as a user, I would like to know why you recommended that song to me. Not because of anything, but also because I really like knowing things, to know the reasons for things. (...) For example, if I know that you recommended a song to me because of X-thing that I listen to a lot, then I know where to look to find similar songs. " (RI 16)

Several interviewees also express how they would love to have the ability to choose between different types of recommender systems, and thus, have more influence on the criteria behind the recommendations (RI 10; 27; 33). As one interviewee explains: *"I would like to have more control over these recommendation algorithms, more transparency - and give me some buttons to press, things I can adjust"* (RI 15).

While many interviewees emphasise transparency, they also express that they might not have the time in their daily life to really utilise the transparency (RI 4; 5; 21; 36). One interviewee (RI 36) points to Spotify Wrapped as a format that is fun to look at, and if it entailed fairness indicators, she might look at them. Thus, this highlights the importance of *how* transparency is communicated, and that it is done creatively and engaging like the 'Spotify Wrapped' feature. Nonetheless, transparency, communicated in the right way, might also be a crucial aspect of creating a good recommendation

system for users, and enhancing user agency might be a valuable step on the path towards a fairer music ecosystem.

A good recommendation creates social connections

A third aspect of a good recommendation system that arose during the interviews was that a good recommendation might also be conceptualised as a recommendation system that fosters social connections and relationships.

Many of the interviewees indeed see music as a social activity. When asked what music gave to them in their everyday life, almost every interviewee also expressed that music's 'superpower', so to say, was the ability to connect them to certain emotions, places or people. Interviewee 18 describes:

"I feel like each song kind of connects me to some people, or some memories of when I heard the song for the first time" (RI 18)

Many interviewees expressed that the platforms allowed them to reconnect easily with music discovered through relationships or lived experiences, and this way allowed them to keep 'connections' alive more readily with past experiences and memories. However, the recommendation systems were still only a minor part of how they discovered new music. Most people still described their main ways of discovering music as being through friends, family or at social events. Seeing music listening habits as a social activity means that auto-play or auto-generated playlists have a limited value. Interviewee 9 describes how she prefers the playlists or recommendations by friends and family due to their personal nature:

"When it's done by a user or by friends or whoever, it's more personalized. So that's different. It's really their taste. (...) I think auto-generated, it's cool if you want something to have it on a background and try to discover other artists that you might not know. (...) So it's different. I prefer the ones that my friends do or that are recommended by my friends than the auto generated ones. But the automatic generated ones are helpful." (RI 9)

Another interviewee, number 17, when asked about how she likes the recommendations she gets, describes her experience like this:

"What Spotify tries to do is... Sometimes, it gives me things that I understand, but it feels like... How can I put it? It feels like it was made in a super weird way. It's like a

person without a face. To answer your question more directly, it's like, "Okay, I get it," but the recommendations feel soulless. I can see that the algorithm is doing its job, but it doesn't really connect with me." (RI 17)

The same interviewee describes how the intention behind the recommendations matters to her:

"I feel like the playlists made by the platform are designed to please me, while the ones made by people reflect their personal taste. There's more of a connection there. It's like a relationship between me, that person, and the music they like or created, and I'm also getting to know the person through their playlist. (...) I like it when the person knows me a little or has some experience with me and says, "Hey, you have to listen to this, I loved it.". I like understanding that someone else liked the song and is sharing it with me, rather than a computer based on my listening history. It feels like I'm just talking to myself." (RI 17)

She is not alone in expressing this sentiment, and other interviewees also pinpoint how the relationship and connection that comes from user-generated playlists or in-person recommendations are valuable to them (RI 2; 20; 36; 19; 16; 18; 27). Interviewee 16 emphasises the feeling of trust that comes with discovering music through friends' playlists:

"(...) It has that element of trust that I get when, for example, I enter a playlist of yours. If I know that we have a similar taste, I know that I'm going to like the songs (...) I think that friends do have more influence and they should be more rewarded in recommendations." (RI 16)

The user-generated playlists are, however, difficult to locate in the interface. One interviewee, when asked if he listens to user-generated playlists, explains: *"Those are so hard to come by - again because Spotify pushes on like those generic Spotify playlists that they have made, they will push that first, so you have to scroll down further or look a bit more to find those user created ones"* (RI 20). He also emphasises that some playlists are difficult to evaluate due to user-generated names that do not say much about the music. When he finds a playlist, e.g. curated by a DJ, it is a way to connect to that DJ and understand the intentions and inspirations behind their music.

A good recommendation from a user perspective can also be conceptualised as a recommendation that manages to connect them to artists, moments and other users. As one person says, when reflecting on what she would change if she were in charge of the streaming service: *"I might like to*

improve the way people socialise through music. I would like to have a better experience sharing with my friends or with my colleagues what we are listening to” (RI 19).

The discovery of music can be driven by one's social connections, but currently, it is impossible to share music across platforms by exporting one's playlists and listening history. This 'lock-in' becomes a major obstacle for people to explore alternative platforms (RI 34; RI 36; RI 9; RI 13) and hinders competition. The sociality of being on the same platform is important for the interviewees.

“I have thought for example about Deezer, that it's kind of carving that path towards fairness, and I have heard recently about the artist-centric... An artist centric system, I don't know, that they're trying out in France. But in Portugal Deezer is not very used, so you know, that would feel kind of lonely because I wouldn't... You know, I wouldn't have anyone to share music with. ” (RI 3)

Another interviewee describes that he is reluctant to change because he has a shared plan with friends and doesn't want to “*leave them hanging*” (RI 9). This is when a user recommends TIDAL to others - as more fair to artists - but continues to use Spotify because it's the most popular platform with most social connections (RI 11). A prerequisite for the growth of fairer platforms is an open-source data-exchange format for playlists, listening histories and social contacts/interactions: The user-generated content and activities, separated from the business logic of the platform.

Sub-conclusion

From our interviews, it is evident that a good recommendation is multifaceted and depends on the interviewee. Three main factors can be seen to contribute to a good recommendation system:

1. giving recommendations that fit the mood / genre of the user
2. being transparent and allowing users to have influence on the recommendation criteria
3. allowing users to connect and giving users the ability to control and share their data across platforms

Accordingly, introducing fairness measures that prioritise promoting emerging or smaller artists to users within their segment would not necessarily compromise user satisfaction. Combined with transparency, fairness measures could help illustrate how music recommendations are made. This could also include allowing users to choose between different types of recommendation criteria. Altogether, our findings suggest that introducing fairness measures into recommendation systems might not be problematic if it's done the right way, and in addition, enhances user agency and control.

Fairness beyond recommendation systems

In the previous sections, we have explored how interviewees conceptualise fairness and to what extent music streaming services and their recommendation systems are seen as promoting or hindering fairness. The findings highlight the duality and complexity of music streaming services' role from a user perspective. Interviewees wish for streaming services to secure fair remuneration and support emerging artists. We have also explored how these wishes align with what interviewees themselves regard as a good recommendation and found that if done in the right way, fairness measures might be compatible with increasing user satisfaction. Furthermore, we have explored that many interviewees consider transparency and control over their own data as a big step towards a fairer streaming industry. Thus, a more collaborative and open-source data infrastructure could be an important step towards a fair music ecosystem from a user perspective.

In this final section, we will explore another aspect raised by the interviewees - namely that for many interviewees the problem of fairness was not seen as rooted in the algorithms or recommendation systems - but instead in the mode of production as well as the incentives structures that drive the business model of the streaming services.

Fairness as moving beyond profit maximisation

During the interviews, it became apparent that algorithms are not really to blame for the lack of fairness. One interviewee bluntly says: *"When we're talking about fairness, I think we can start with not going into capitalism would be a good start, yes? Or not things being done for profit, or so much for profit"* (RI 14). About half of the participants expressed a similar frustration with for-profit companies like Spotify, Apple and YouTube Music. Some interviewees (RI 16; 27; 3; 32; 20) were outspoken in their critique of the economic logic behind the platforms, others expressed their frustration in more subtle ways like interviewee 17: *"I think they should promote lesser-known artists, but I understand that in a capitalist world, platforms will promote whoever brings them the most money."* (RI 17). Most interviewees express a similar understanding of this supposed paradox - that they wished for the platforms to prioritise smaller artists, but that they simply didn't see it as realistic given the economic logic of the platforms. As one interviewee says: *"I know it will never happen. It's like talking about sharing the world's wealth. Inequalities are growing. I think that in music, too, inequalities are growing."* (RI 26). When asked if equal distribution through the recommendation systems is important to him, interviewee 28 explains:

"In fact, I wouldn't put the issue there. It's more a question of production. Production conditions have to be fair. At least, that's the way I see it, but I think that if production

conditions were fair, and not biased by a whole host of factors, distribution in itself wouldn't be a problem. (...) In fact, it's very likely that if we took an interest in the conditions of production and ensured that they were fair, there would be no recommendation algorithm.” (RI 28)

The interviewee continues:

“What pushes artists forward is not based on content. It's not the artist's musical universe, whether it's the music they produce or the image they give of themselves, that feeds the algorithm per se, but rather a kind of feedback from the effects on the use of the platform itself. The platform seeks to maximise its audience and, behind that audience, its profitability. This is in fact the factor that explains the effects of recommendation algorithms, which can then be interpreted as beneficial effects because they will be more profitable. At a certain point, the platform needs to highlight emerging artists because it's also a way of attracting people to the platform. This has beneficial effects, but it can also have more negative effects, locking people into listening to tracks that are profitable. Multiplying the number of listens to things that will occupy people's mental space, but fundamentally it's not the content of the music itself that counts. Which is why I don't think there's any algorithm, or at least there's no fair recommendation in that sense. None of the platform operators will admit or publicly communicate the fact that what guides their decisions, that the implementation of their services has nothing to do with music.” (RI 28)

Several interviewees also argue that this search for sustaining and growing profits is reinforced by the algorithmic logic of maximising or optimising engagement (RI 35; 20). Interviewee 8 observes the effect of this logic:

“I think music has become really safe (...) it just fits a mould that will satisfy the people that or that will entertain the people and sometimes music can be made to challenge some preconceptions some prejudices (...) I think this algorithm based listening is so fast and that has to do of course with the attention span becoming less and less or becoming smaller - I think music really has to be safe in order to have more guarantee of success commercial success so I think the algorithm mirrors that. It fits the expectations.” (RI 8)

Thus, some interviewees are frustrated with the search for, as they see it, commercial success being put above other factors. Another interviewee adds the following and calls for new measures of success to be put forward: *“Yes, success is based on a number of sales. In fact, it's based on an economic calculation when there could be other indicators of success for artists.”* (RI 27). One interviewee explains that he only sees this problem getting worse with the newest technological development and AI, where the amount of music being generated to increase profits will become too much for the user to absorb (RI 33). Another reflects on how, while he really loves the big catalogue, he at the same time also misses the simplicity of the iPod stage, because the inherently limited selection available allowed him a better overview and control and thus left him feeling less overwhelmed (RI 15).

While interviewees express a frustration with this logic, many of them also simultaneously accept it as a given and unchangeable fact. When reflecting on the dominance of popular artists within the recommendations that she receives, one interviewee explains:

“They can promote artists that are already popular, and I understand that they have to, because if they didn't promote artists that are already popular, maybe listeners wouldn't be subscribed to those platforms” (RI 1).

Thus, she - and many other interviewees - express not only frustration but also understanding that the platforms *have to* prioritise growing and sustaining their user-base as well as their profits. Among many interviewees, there is a simultaneous acceptance of the profit-driven logic of the platforms, deeply interlinked with a wish for the platforms to break out of this logic. One expresses the paradox between the ideal and reality like this: *“Ideally, they would have a role in adding more to their listener, i think yeah but at the end of the day they are a business and... How would you make them have that role?”* (RI 8). Many interviewees also acknowledge that the role of labels might make it difficult for streaming services to prioritise differently. One interviewee argues that while users are important for streaming services like Spotify, he believes that their *“business model is all reliant on how much money they can get from their relationships with labels, especially the major ones.”* (RI 14). Several other interviewees also point to the labels as the main problem (RI 4; 6; 7; 17; 24), and some even point to the music streaming services as just reinforcing, in a more hidden manner, the power of the labels (RI 20; RI 6). Indicating that fairness seems also to be conceptualised as something that cannot just be fixed by tinkering with new measurements, but as something more inherent in the logics that drive the business.

Several interviewees express that fairness relates to issues such as proper taxation and ethical investment policies. As one interviewee says, when asked what he would do differently as the boss of Spotify: *“Perhaps not using Spotify's money to fund wars would be a good idea”* (RI 14). Another interviewee asks:

“Do they pay taxes in the countries where they operate? (...) that money could be reinvested in local artists through state programs or our live shows or whatever that would be a kind of philanthropy way to give back to the - not necessarily to the particular artists - but to the whole community. ” (RI 8).

This can be seen as reflecting the same tendency, that interviewees wish the platforms would take a bigger responsibility *‘beyond profit’* (RI 3) and for reinvesting the wealth created in ethical ways that help sustain and regenerate local music scenes. Another interviewee (RI 27) expresses that she is frustrated with the system that constantly seeks to expand and instead wishes the industry could find a *“stable economic model”* based on subscriptions instead of relying on advertisements and labels. She further adds that she wishes for a change in the way artists are remunerated:

“I'd be very happy for the creative process if artists were paid, and in that case we could kill off the intellectual property that's based on listening. Instead, we'd be paid for the time it takes to do something, so we'd be paying the artist. He'll be able to eat for as long as he makes his creation, but for the rest, he won't be relying on intellectual property. He'll continue to work and it's true that somewhere along the line, I think it would be more logical, in the logic of open source. I don't know if that makes sense.”
(RI 27)

She elaborates:

“It would be much more interesting if artists all had a role to play in society and that rather than doing a concert where they're going to be paid, I don't know how much, that they're paid just like someone who works to do good things and is therefore paid all year to create, to give talks in classes or in nursing homes, whatever. ” (RI 27)

This suggests that interviewees conceptualise fairness as a problem that goes beyond the recommendation systems and the platforms themselves.

Ambivalent users between ideals and reality

Many interviewees felt ambivalent about using the platforms and about the aforementioned incoherence between *ideal* and *reality*. As one interviewee expressed: *“I don't think any of these platforms strike me as fair in relation to the artists. So it's been like having to 'bite the sour apple'”* (RI 15). Thus, expressing that it is unpleasant to have to accept the conditions, but necessary as he sees a lack of good alternatives. Another interviewee explains that she feels it's not the most ethical choice, but that she still uses it:

“I know that even though I'm paying for Spotify Premium, I'm really just paying a giant company that isn't giving much to the artists. It's like buying clothes from a big brand—you know it's not the most ethical choice.” (RI 17).

This slight discomfort with supporting the platforms despite the lack of fair remuneration to the artists is adamant in almost all of the interviews, and especially the interviewees who had friends and family in the music industry (RI 17; 12). One interviewee explains:

“I have friends in music and it's just heartbreaking, because they go through a whole process and invest so much time, money and thoughts into their work and then for that not to be compensated somehow just it's not fair” (RI 13).

Thus, despite this underlying frustration with how their music listening habits affect artists, none of the interviewees have changed their platform of choice solely based on perceptions of fairness. One interviewee explains: *“I changed streaming platforms for reasons of integration into an ecosystem (...) But the fact that Apple Music pays more for artists than Spotify, for me, it's also important.”* (RI 2). The few interviewees who have changed platforms to a perceived 'more fair' platform express a similar logic. It seems that the fairness aspect has not been the driving force but has been one among many aspects they have considered. The most important aspects relate more to sound quality, size of the music catalogue, price and ability to share music with social connections (RI 13; 9; 17; 19; 20; 14). As interviewee 9 says:

“I heard of other platforms that pay more to the artists but it's hard for me to change when the algorithm - it's well fine-tuned for my... for what I like - and when I split the plan with other people... so I don't want to like to leave and then leave them hanging... that's probably the main reason that I haven't left and go for another platform. (...) if I were to change, it would probably be for TIDAL - because the sound quality is better, they pay better for the artists.” (RI 9)

When asked directly if fairness is an important aspect for him when choosing his streaming platform, another interviewee confesses:

“I would like to say yes, and I think yes, but have I done anything to correct it? I think not... because I guess the convenience side plays that big of a role in the way I listen to music. I like to compensate when I buy vinyl and stuff but I know it's not really...”
(RI 8)

Almost all interviewees mentioned a tension between what felt important and their own actions. An interviewee who was very adamant in his critique of Spotify admits that despite his ramming critique of their business model, he has been reluctant to shift: *“I already have a lot of stuff on Spotify, and I'm a lazy son of a bitch sometimes. So, I didn't feel like switching in all honesty.”* (RI 14). Another interviewee expresses a similar sentiment: *“I have thought about changing platforms because of that [lack of fair remuneration]. I think I haven't done it just for a matter of laziness and practicality, and the fact that I like the platform I'm using now. And it's not one of the worst, too.”* (RI 3). Another interviewee emphasises that the comfort of the streaming services wins him over, even though he tries to use platforms he perceives as fairer:

“I mostly use streaming services like SoundCloud and Spotify (...) I hate to admit it but I probably mostly use Spotify because the catalogue is bigger and the interface is easier to use for me as a user (...) the impatient part of me wins” (RI 33).

There is thus a seeming duality that interviewees are uncomfortable with the streaming services' way of treating artists, but at the same time, too comfortable with it to make them change their choice of platform. One interviewee explains how he deals with these conflicting feelings:

“It [fair remuneration] is important, yes, but I see the contradiction because I also want to get access to music and I know the price is cheap (...) that's why I mostly go to concerts and try to support people that way.” (RI 7)

Instead of changing platforms, about half of the interviewees expressed that to deal with their bad conscience over using streaming platforms, they compensated by buying records, concert tickets and other merchandise from time to time (RI 19; 20; 21; 33; 15; 9; 12). One interviewee explains how she tries to practice her own version of 'fair trade':

"I use Spotify to check out new albums, and if I like it, I'll buy it. It's my way of doing "fair trade," so to speak. (...) I'm aware that the artist isn't getting much from Spotify, so I try to compensate by buying their work later. " (RI 17).

For some interviewees, the idea of switching to a smaller library, and thus giving up the access to all sorts of music, is also a big barrier that means they are reluctant to change platforms (RI 20; 15). Interviewee 17 explains:

"Imagine that I switch to a super fair platform, but it only has 20 albums. I'm not tempted to switch if that's the alternative. As a user, I'm paying, let's say, 10 or 12 euros, and on Spotify, I have millions of albums. It's not like certain cinema platforms, where you pay a monthly fee but still have to pay extra for certain films. That might be fairer, but for the user, it's not as appealing. What would be cooler is if all platforms offered everything for the price you already pay, even if it was a bit more expensive. I'd be willing to pay twice as much, or even triple, if the catalogue was as comprehensive as Spotify's but with fairer compensation for artists." (RI 17)

Another interviewee says:

"I was considering [another platform that is perceived as more fair by the interviewee] but it ended up being a little more expensive and at the end of the day (...) we are people with bills to pay yeah and that plays a huge role in these kinds of decisions as well (...) I think you are there are some decisions that you are not allowed to make very ethically or a harder to make at least" (RI 8)

Several also express that they haven't really heard of any good alternatives that have the same to offer in terms of catalogue and price. For interviewees, catalogue size and price are drivers of choice more than fairness. It is also clear that very few interviewees feel they can have a big impact by moving platforms. As interviewee 28 says:

"Today I think that the way I consume music has little impact, little effect on remuneration, on the way remuneration should be distributed for artists. (...) I can only contribute to their remuneration by walking. I don't think I have much influence on that front" (RI 28)

Interviewee 3 expresses a similar sentiment in that while in theory interviewees have a responsibility, she feels the reach of changing her consumption is limited:

“If everyone started moving to better and more fair services, they would have to change things. But, you know, that's the thing about a lot of issues in our day. Like, I mean... It's not a very good comparison, but it's the one that's coming to my mind, it's the same with climate change. Of course, if everyone stopped using plastic straws and started eating less meat, less fish, and whatever, the world would change. But it's not like... It's a limited reach.” (RI 3).

Some interviewees also explain that they experience their own contribution and responsibility gets a bit lost in the complexity of the system (RI 15; 29). One of them explains:

“Recently I've been asking myself this question: how do artists earn a living? Because before, it was more transparent. Well, not that it was more transparent, but it was more logical because they were selling albums and CDs. It was the object and it was physical. I knew that when I bought an album or a CD, the artist was potentially going to get something. But now, when I listen to a song on Spotify or YouTube, I often wonder. I ask myself: the more I listen to a song, does the artist behind it get something, or is it the streaming platform? I don't know. “ (RI 29)

Nonetheless, many interviewees highlight that both users and platforms hold a shared responsibility for changing the sector and ‘adapting’ to the new ecosystem. One interviewee says: *“I don't think it depends on Spotify (...) It's the way that I use the service, not the service...what the service offers me. (...) I think it's my responsibility to...to look for and, uh, pay more attention.”* (RI 5). Though at the same time, she expresses that she doesn't really have time to investigate whether the remuneration conditions are fair, or if recommendations are biased. Therefore, while interviewees express frustration and discomfort with the perceived unfair conditions in the music streaming market, most of them are reluctant or perhaps too comfortable to switch platforms, and only a few have a strong belief in their ability to change the conditions.

Thus, most interviewees expect improvements to come from the streaming platforms and express a wish for them to take on more responsibility (RI 16; 21; 33; 3). As one interviewee says: *“With great power comes great responsibility”* (RI 19). Another explains:

“I think that both the platforms have more leverage. Personally, yes, I would want to increase whatever the artist gets, but that is not going to change the economic model that the platforms are going to follow. So I think that that's why, you know, there has

to be some control entities that can encourage, let's say, the big platforms to act more fairly.” (RI 7)

Interviewee 33 points to the role of the music streaming sector also in devaluing the market and getting users accustomed to pay very little for cultural products such as music:

“The willingness to pay for cultural products is there (...) but when you feed a market where it becomes cheaper and cheaper, and it has to be cheaper, you are a part of pulling the consumer into a market where “Spotify is only DKK 100, so why go and pay DKK 200” (...) They have been part of undermining the market... The counter argument is then that people are at least willing to pay for a streaming service, we generate a lot of money (...) my point is that music and culture has been devalued and this means less money in the sector, and it difficult for artists to make a living” (RI 33)

While interviewees recognise their own role in the problem, most emphasise that the platforms should take responsibility for a transition to a fairer music ecosystem since they have had a role in creating the current system and they are perceived to have the most leverage. Moreover, many interviewees are too comfortable with the convenience of the streaming service, and this often wins over the discomfort they feel with the perceived unfair conditions.

Conclusion

In this study, we obtained several important insights into how interviewees conceptualise fairness and how they perceive music streaming services and their recommendation systems, in relation to the ambition of a more fair music ecosystem.

First of all, our findings highlight that interviewees view music streaming services as having a dual role in relation to fairness. Music streaming services are both seen as a catalyst for a more fair and diverse music market since so many more musicians and users are now able to connect on the platforms. At the same time, music streaming services are perceived as also posing several obstacles to fairness due to unfair remuneration practices and biased recommendations skewed towards popular artists. While interviewees express that the recommendation systems do allow them to discover some niche or independent artists, most interviewees also express a wish for the platforms to take a bigger responsibility in supporting emerging or smaller artists.

Secondly, we also explored how interviewees conceptualise a 'good recommendation'. We explored whether their expectations for more fair recommendations aligned with what they described as a good recommendation. While the answers differed, we found that there can be decoded at least three main aspects of a good recommendation system: 1) a system that provides music similar to their music taste, 2) a system that is transparent and allows users to influence recommendation criteria, and 3) a system that prioritizes building connections between users as well as artists and enables sharing data across platforms. Hence, introducing fairness measures that promote emerging artists within users' regular genres and preferences can be seen as compatible with a good recommendation system - especially if it is done in a transparent manner and allows users agency in the process.

Furthermore, our findings open a discussion doubting whether recommendation systems are the most meaningful place of intervention when tackling the lack of a fair music ecosystem. Many interviewees highlight that the problem of fairness is not rooted there, and refer instead to other factors, such as 1) the underlying economic logic of profit maximisation, 2) the role of labels, and 3) taxation and investments of profits, as possible areas to intervene in for a fairer music streaming ecosystem.

Lastly, while these findings give us insight into the user perspective on the question of fairness within the music streaming ecosystem, it is important to note that our interviewees only represent a very small segment of the European MSS' users, therefore, in order to consolidate our findings, further and more extensive research is needed.

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